

Map of Special Need Education Service Problems the Pandemic Era of Covid-19 in Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 07, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: February 11, 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning Media, Social Skills, Children with Developmental barriers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14851786</p>	<p><i>Long distance learning for children with special needs, especially in the pandemic era, brings many challenges. This study aims to obtain an overview of the latest education services for children with special needs during the pandemic, to understand the roles of parents and teachers in services for children with special needs, as well as service barriers for children with special needs. This research is a qualitative and quantitative research. Methods of data collection that used were distributing questionnaires, focus group discussion, and interviews. Observations were made at 10 special schools and inclusive schools in DKI Jakarta, Depok and Tangerang, interviews were conducted with 3 kindergarten teachers, 2 elementary school teachers, and 3 parents. The survey was conducted on 49 teachers and 38 parents at kindergarten and elementary school levels as classroom teachers and assisting teachers for children with special needs in inclusive schools in Jabodetabek, Central Java, Kalimantan and Pekanbaru. Qualitative data analysis was carried out using the triangulation technique consisted of the stages of data collection, data reduction, data display, and verification or data conclusion. Quantitative data analysis was performed by calculating the frequency. The results of the study explained that educational services during a pandemic were carried out by modifying meetings, curricula and assignments. The role of parents is very important in a pandemic, and the obstacles that are passed by teachers, parents and children with special needs.</i></p>

Introduction

Educational services for children with special needs in Indonesia are still far from expectations. There are many obstacles in the field, even though government regulations have regulated Permendikbud number 70 of 2009 concerning inclusive education for students who have disabilities and have the potential for intelligence and / or special talents (Regulation of the Minister of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia Number 70, 2009). In this regulation, there is an obligation for public and private schools to accept students with special needs to get the same treatment without discrimination.

Even though there is a quota rule for admission of children with special needs in public elementary schools, because it is indeed limited in admission, this makes parents looking for other alternatives so that their children can be accepted at public schools. Based on an interview with a public elementary school teacher in the Cempaka Putih area, the admission of special needs students did not start with any assessment activities. In addition, there is no transparency from the parents regarding the condition of their children, because they are worried that the school will not accept their children to attend school.

The choice of public school is still being the dream and choice of parents, considering that the cost of education in private schools is quite high and feels very heavy for the general public. In terms of population, children with special needs in each region vary in number. The number of children with special needs in Indonesia, according to CNN data in 2016, is around 12.15%, which is spread throughout Indonesia (CNN data, 2016), while BPS 2017 data for the number of children with special needs is 1.6 (Data from the Central Statistics Agency, 2016; Shelly, 2019).

From the total of data it shows that not all children with special needs have received school education services, whether they are accepted in inclusive schools or special schools because of not all regions in Indonesia provide this service. Meanwhile teacher with special education qualifications is still limited, and not all schools have them. Because of the limited access to formal education, many children with special needs do not receive formal education, and families have no choice, and finally care for their children and educate them in their home.

For example in the Sebatik area, it is recorded that in the UPT Education Office (Andi; 2020) there are 11 children needing services, this does not include data on children who may not report to the District Education Office, because the unavailability of either inclusive or special schools on Sebatik Island and parents have to send their children outside the island. Likewise, service data in Tanah Grogot District, Paser Regency East

Kalimantan Province, Indonesia has implemented inclusive classes in 8 public elementary schools, but unfortunately in the 2016/2017 school year these schools refused to accept ABK (children with special needs) with the reason that there were no special supervisors.

Meanwhile, the data of the Section of Educator and Education District Staff of the Kulon Progo Regency Education Office (2015) that the number of children with special needs in 2015 reached 730 students with special needs, while the teachers who served children with special needs were 341 Special Advisors Teacher (GPK). It is not just a matter of numbers, but GPKs do not have a special educational background, while only 89 teachers have attended training on inclusive education and 252 teachers have never attended training on inclusive education so that teachers feel confused in serving children with special needs. In addition, they only visit school twice a week, and can't accompany the ABK every day, so that GPK has not been able to serve ABK optimally, likewise the homeroom teacher only helps to care and give the attention but not maximally.

The result of survey from 165 teachers and 35 parents of children with special needs from Jabodetabek show that 79% stated that they did not have the knowledge and skills about children with special needs, they did not understand what happened to the children and also did not have skills to handle it. The weakness that still occur in the field, could be because of the implementation of the policy is still in process, and this is also acknowledged by the Minister of Education and Culture (Mendikbud) of the Republic of Indonesia Muhadjir Effendy, as quoted by Malang Pos, that the new Government was paying more attention to students with special needs or people with disabilities in the last two or three years. Meanwhile, only about 20% of students with special needs were served, so that many students with special needs do not go to school or study at home with their families and the community.

Meanwhile, in the Covid-19 pandemic era, the Government through the Indonesian Minister of Education and Culture Circular Letter Number 03 of 2020 concerning the Prevention of Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19) in the Education Unit, and the Letter of the Secretary General of the Indonesian Minister of Education and Culture number 35492 / A.A5 / HK / 2020 dated 12 March 2020 concerning the Prevention of Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19), provides a school from home policy for all children, including children with special needs. Not only schools have stopped their activities, but various other gathering activities such as offices, markets and entertainment areas. Because the Covid-19 virus is so dangerous and up to this time there is no anti-virus has been found, and based on this situation, teaching and learning activities and school administration activities are still online. The government plans to open schools in January 2021, in the next semester, but this policy is also depend on the District Education Office and local government offices. Remembering that several regions in Indonesia still have high levels of covid-19 transmission.

Based on the preliminary study, there were obstacles in some schools and certain areas related to the implementation of learning at home. Indeed, not all of the implementation learning process by online learning, some using offline, or a combination of the two things. The obstacles that are often complained about online are network problems, as well as the use of technology that not all teachers able to use it

Meanwhile, not all students also have online learning devices such as gadgets or laptops. In handling children with special needs, it was found that there were schools that had completely closed and no activities, due to the lack of cooperation from parents (Interview to teacher of Jakarta and Depok area, 2020). This is being a challenge for parents and teachers to adapt to the existing situation. Due to the forecast for today's situation and for some time to come. Learning services will still be carried out online, as well as student admission or other administration done online, this can be a gap for undetected children who need special services. In Kompas.com, Joko Juwono stated that the parents of children with special needs certainly need time to adapt to the Covid-19 situation and the biggest challenge is how learning and guiding activities with parents at home can be carried out as well as possible (Kompas.com, 2020).

The use of internet facilities, gadgets may be familiar to our society, the use of various online facilities such as zoom, video calls on *WhatsApp* and internet facilities that are accessed in almost all regions of Indonesia. Network constraints sometimes occur, but communication can still be done to various regions, also the subsidized internet quota from the government is very helpful for successful communication between teachers and parents. On the positive side, learning carried out through an online system requires students and teachers to improve their competencies related to the use of technology to support the learning process (Puspitasari, 2020; Sari, Tussyantari, and Suswandari, 2021).

These various obstacles have become a concern in mapping research on education services for children with special needs in the pandemic era in Indonesia. This qualitative and quantitative study to parents and teachers in various regions in Indonesia aims to: 1) Obtain data on problems related to education services for children with special needs during the pandemic, 2) What is the role parents and teachers in ABK services, 3) obstacle of services for children with special needs.

Literature Review

The research results of Auladi, et al. (2020) show that the obstacles experienced by teachers in learning during the Covid-19 pandemic consisted of educators' unpreparedness at the beginning of the application of distance learning and problems related to lack of internet connections, lack of parent assistance, and students who are getting bored (Auladi, Khanan, et al, 2020). Problems related to the obstacles faced during the face to face distance learning have caused many problems especially at the Preschool and Elementary levels, this thought has led the PAUD and Dikmas Directorate of Ministry of Education and Culture immediately (PAUD director, BIMTEK APE assistance, 2021). Constraints related to the implementation of learning in the field are actually a form of teacher adaptation and encourage teachers to increase their competences and be professional in any condition (Ulum and Mukhlisina, 2017).

The successful of the implementation of learning for children with special needs is influenced by various aspects, namely teachers, parents, and school management, government, community, and school equipment and infrastructure. Problems related to teachers are the limited number of accompanying teachers who have special education backgrounds, students with various specialties who require different handling of each child, management and involvement of parents and the community (NissaTornato, 2016). This is also stated by Giangreco (2013) that schools also have to collaborate with the school community such as teachers, class companion teachers, parents, students, school administrative teams, and school communities to maximize teacher performance. Ecological theory Bronfenbrenner, someone from Cornell University, United States state that human development is influenced by the environmental context. The reciprocal relationship between the individual and the environment will shape the individual's behavior. Information on the environment where children live describe, organize and clarify the effects of various environments. Ecological theory tries to look at human interactions in a system or subsystem. Ecological theory views the development of children from three environmental systems, namely microsystems, ecosystems, and macrosystems. These three systems assist individual development in forming certain physical and mental characteristics. The explanation of the three systems can be described as follows:

Figure 1. Ecology Human Development Theory

Method

This study used qualitative research with descriptive method. Observations were made in 10 special schools and inclusive schools in the DKI Jakarta, Depok and Tangerang areas, interviews were conducted with 3 kindergarten teachers, 2 elementary school teachers, and 3 parents. The survey was distributed to 87 people consisting of 49 teachers and 38 parents at kindergarten and elementary school as classroom teachers and teachers for children with special needs in inclusive schools from several regions in Indonesia such as Jabodetabek, Central Java, Kalimantan and Pekanbaru.

The data were collected using questionnaires, focus group discussions, and interviews involving parents, teachers, and experts. The collected data analyzed using the triangulation technique consisted of the stages of data collection, data reduction, data display, and verification or data conclusion.

Results and Discussion

Based on data obtained in the field during the pandemic, we found data on the impact of education services as follow:

Education Services

Face to face of teachers and children

Based on the results of observations to 10 schools in the DKI Jakarta area and its surroundings, school teaching and learning process is generally by online, without face to face, as well as for education services for children with special needs. The survey was conducted on 87 person consisting of 49 teachers and 38 parents from regions in Indonesia, and the result are 73% of learning was conducted online, 25% was face-to-face and 2% using a combination of online and face-to-face.

Diagram 1. Teacher meeting service of teacher and student on pandemic situation

In interviews with District Education Office of the Sebatik region, also in Pekanbaru and Kalimantan, the implementation of ABK services was carried out home visit by teacher to give and explain about their assignments and then taking them back. Likewise to several remote areas that do not have cellphone facilities, as well as difficulties in internet networks. .

Even though the situation is pandemic and haveto maintain physical distancing, some parents choose to bring teachers home to guide their children. This is usually done at the kindergarten level, and also in areas that are included in the green zone with low covid-19 cases. Meanwhile, in high Covid-19 cases such as DKI Jakarta, West Java, Solo, East Java, and several areas affected by Covid-19 with high cases, parents prefer let their children to stay at home and study online.

Another way that schools do is by face-to-face activities with health protocols and paying attention to physical distancing, like taking turns of student in attending to school, which is twice a week. From the survey on 87 person consisted of 49 teachers and 38 parents from regions in Indonesia, show that teaching and learning process 20% were conducted face-to-face at school, 24% stated that teachers came to their homes and 53% were still conducted online without being face to face. And the rest is done face to face more than twice a week.

Figure 2. Teaching learning process in the pandemic situation

Face-to-face activity were still held with various considerations. 58.7% were requests from parents, 15.9% were due to difficulties in getting to the internet and 25.4% were due to school policies.

Figure 3. Teacher-child meeting service during a pandemic

Another finding was that there were schools for children with special need in Depok that did not carry out activities at all during the pandemic, especially at the kindergarten and elementary levels. While some parents choose to take part in the home schooling program, there are also parents choose to postpone register their children to school while waiting for the pandemic low so the schools can carry out normal activities. They considered that online learning was not effective for children with special needs, because parents had to spend sufficient time to guide their children while studying at home.

Curriculum Service

The findings related to the curriculum of learning in inclusive schools are not evenly distributed, there are many schools do not have special service teachers for children in special need special schools, so children with special needs are still handled intensively by a teacher. From the observation that held in 5 schools in Jakarta and Depok, found that these schools did not have a special education service program in schools starting from: early assessment, no special teacher for children in special need, and the teachers did not have individual education programs.

A survey related to curriculum services in inclusive schools, conducted on 165 teachers in Jabodetabek, obtained data: 84% of schools did not carry out assessment activities in admitting students with special needs in schools, even interviewing 5 teachers they did not understand what problems happened to their students. Especially in the midst of a pandemic situation like this, the student admission process is carried out online. During learning, routine meetings are also rarely held, 85% of teachers in schools do not hold regular meetings to discuss learning programs for children with special needs 79% of schools do not make special learning programs. The survey data is depicted in the following diagram:

Figure 4 Curriculum for Children with Special Needs Program at School

Interviews conducted with 5 teachers in kindergarten and elementary school stated that teachers' knowledge is still lacking about the characteristics of children with special needs and how to deal with them. The concept of child services with special needs for a number of teachers is still a formidable challenge.

Assignment Service

A survey of 87 kindergarten and elementary school teachers and parents found that the provision of educational services such as the delivery of materials was carried out by 44.5% by sending instructional videos, 27.2% asking children to read textbooks, 23.5% of providing material with face to face advance online, and the rest takes material from the internet.

Figure 5 Material delivery services from teacher

The assignments given were carried out by students recording assignments in the form of video recordings totaling 43.8%, and 36.3% working on assignments from books answering questions on Google Form, and others sending assignments via paper sheets and collecting photos of their assignments.

Based on interviews to n 3 kindergarten teachers, 2 elementary school teachers, and 3 parents, it was also found that the assignment given by the teacher were not only academic learning, but the teacher also gave various tasks related to activities at home, a light job with the family. Such as activities in making food with mothers, watering plants, raising animals, sweeping, mopping, practicing worship, as well as creative activities such as making films via cellphones, drawing, making crafts and doing various science experiments accompanied by parents at home.

The assignment from teacher was collected by the student in various ways as mentioned above, and if the children have not collected their assignment, the teacher will remind the parents in the *WhatsApp* group so that the children can immediately complete the assignment, or the teacher calls directly, and if there is serious obstacles faced by parents, they can meet the teacher directly with the child at home.

Figure 6 Form of service assignment from teacher

Role of Parent

Based on the of interviews with 3 kindergarten teachers, 2 elementary school teachers, and 3 parents, shows that the success of the online learning process for children with special needs is depend on the role of parents at home. All tasks assigned by the teacher and therapist are done by parents at home. For parents who are both busy for working, this is a bit troublesome so they have to take turn to take care their children or wait until the parents are finished with work or accompany their children to study on their free time of their time busy with WFH and other household chores.

Figure 7 Daring Perception

However, the results of a survey from 38 parents at kindergarten and elementary school level found that 55.2% of them stated that online activities at home made them have more time with their children, while 41.4% had difficulty helping children learning, the rest of them parents became more learning get to know the child, although sometimes it causes emotional and impatient attitude of parents. 35.6% of parents and teachers, as well as academics agree that the role of parents is more important in fostering children's social skills, 63% agree that there is a need for collaboration between parents and teachers, only a few say that it is the role of the teacher alone.

Figure 8 Perception about Parent and Teacher role

Learning Obstacle

Obstacle of Parent and Teacher

Based on the results of interviews conducted by parents and teachers, the learning situation at home has many obstacles. This is usually related to network constraints, especially in areas with limited access, cellphones are only owned by parents, parents have to fully accompany children to study.

Meanwhile, from the results of observations conducted in 2 schools and interviews with 3 teachers in the DKI Jakarta area, it was found that the implementation of online ABK services during the pandemic had increased the burden on teachers; taking the time that sometimes does not know the time to contact parents regarding children's duties. The problem with cellphone facilities that only parents have is that teachers have to wait for parents to come home from work so that children can collect their assignments.

Meanwhile, according to data from 87 teachers and parents from several regions of Indonesia, either parents or teachers show that 27.2% are network constrained, 24.7% stated that teachers have difficulty with teaching online to children with special needs, 40.7% parents do not understand assisting children to learn, and the rest is due to no one accompanies the child to study at home.

Figure 9 the Obstacle of Online Learning

Constraints related to the problem of collaboration between parents and teachers according to parents and teachers often become obstacles in handling children, in ordinary situations especially during pandemic situations where communication is carried out online and limitation of time to meeting in person.

Based on the results of interviews with 3 kindergarten teachers, 2 elementary school teachers, and 3 parents show that the biggest obstacle to learning for children with special needs during the pandemic is on the child's independence, and relatively full guidance by parents at home. Children have to be assisted in understanding the concept of subject matter, doing assignments, and evaluating, as part of academic activities. Thus, the development of life skills becomes the full duty of parents, such as advice children to have a good attitude, good communication, and train children's responsibility at home.

Regarding academic assignments from the survey of 87 teachers and parents found that the constraints on children's understanding of subjects were 58.7% in mathematics and science, 9.3% of children's constraints on religious subjects, the rest were constraints on understanding Indonesian Language subject. Other lessons also have different problems for each child and there are children who have problems in all subject areas.

Figure 10 Constraint of Student Understanding

In the learning process and the handling of children with special needs, data found that 40.4% of children have communication problems which became obstacles to the learning process in the classroom, 21.2% of children had difficulty gaining the ability to be independent, while 22.8% of children had problems with social interaction, and 15.8% had difficulty showing their expressions / emotions appropriately to those around them.

Picture 11 Social Skill of Children

Problems related to communication it show that 35.1% have difficulty understanding other people, 31.6% of children do not focus on speaking, 21.1% of children's language is difficult to understand, and 12.3% of children often repeat words. The problem of children's social interaction is known that 48.3% of children have behaviors that are difficult for children to accept, 25.9% of children have difficulty sitting still, 13.8% prefer to be alone, and 12.1% of behavior disturbing others. Independent behavior of children with special needs show that 62.1% of children need great help from their surroundings, 29.3% of children need assistance in doing academic activities / school assignments. Meanwhile, 8.6% of children are able to carry out activities independently.

Results and Discussion

Map of problems in education services for children with needs during the pandemic, focused on education services, what are the role of parents, and the obstacles faced by both teachers, parents and children themselves. The result of discussion will be described as follows:

Education Services

Children with Special Needs services during the pandemic in Indonesia which is focused on this research are related to meeting face-to-face services between teacher and student, curriculum services and teacher assignment services. Considering the pandemic situation that began around March 2020 and is still ongoing at the time of this writing that is December 2020, there is an appeal from the Government and District Education Service to prohibit the community have activities outside the home. Then gradually, work activities have been allowed but by implementing strict health protocols, considering that the number of victims exposed to Covid-19 is still quite high.

With the number of cases exposed as of 20 December 2020 is 163,111 for the DKI Jakarta area with around 3,087 (1.9%) fatalities [12], the DKI Jakarta Regional Government does not provide room for learning services other than using online, while other areas such as in Tangerang, Kalimantan, Pekanbaru, Papua, Sebatik, they still use face to face learning, or do it in combination. Meetings online make learning for children with special needs have many obstacles. Children with special needs who need a lot of guidance and touch are constrained by limited meetings with teachers. Some places continue to do face-to-face activities so that learning can run well. This was done based on data that 58.7% due to the requests from parents who had difficulty guiding their children to learn, and also because there were no facilities for online learning.

There are still obstacles in the curriculum service considering that there are still many schools that do not have early assessment facilities, there are no special supervisors at schools, and teachers do not have individual education programs. Early assessment is needed in an effort to identify children's characteristics, weaknesses and strengths. Not all schools that serve children with special needs in schools have teachers who have special educational backgrounds, so both the knowledge and skills of teachers are far from expectations. Likewise, the learning program is carried out by the teacher by modifying learning so that it can be followed by students. Some creative teachers develop learning programs in accordance with the characteristics of the child.

Then the teacher tries to teach in a pandemic situation by providing materials and assignments to children both online and face-to-face. The material was delivered by the teacher in limited terms, using various media such as video recordings, textbooks, the internet and given directly face-to-face both online and in person.

Educational services are also carried out by providing good academic assignments, as well as tasks that are useful for the development of children's social skills. The assignments are given by the teacher, where students

collect results using video, Google form, and textbooks. Meanwhile, other tasks such as activities at home and creativity are given as variations so that children do not become bored at home. Tasks are collected by parents from teachers through existing social media. The teacher also reminds the parents, if the child has not done the task and the teacher periodically contacts the parents, sometimes the teacher picks up the assignment of the child who has not done it and helps complete the task.

Figure 12 Education Service on Pandemic Situation

From the data collected it show that, it can be seen that learning during a pandemic requires various changes. If it is related to things to do the learning process of children with special needs, learning must be based on the results of the assessment which then become the basis for each student's learning. The results of this assessment form the basis for making individual learning programs. Translation of curriculum through individual learning programs is needed by students with special needs (ArtafantiandPandia, 2018), especially during this pandemic (Arta, 2018). If teachers do not understand how to provide appropriate educational services, especially during this pandemic, various trainings need to be continuously provided to develop teachers' abilities and skills (Song, 2016). Teachers need to have the ability and willingness to provide the best service for students with special needs, because as stated by Spektor-Levy and Yifrach (2017), teachers need to adapt learning techniques, evaluation, and various things needed when accepting students with special needs in class (Webster-Stratton and Bywater, 2015).

Role of Parent

Learning in pandemic conditions for children with special needs is indeed quite hard for parents and teachers to feel. Moreover, schools have no preparation in implementation, so that both teachers, parents and children are required to adapt quickly. As the activity progressed, some teachers began to get used to online learning using zoom, *WhatsApp* and other forms of social media. For teachers who are not familiar with technology, especially teachers who are over 50 years old, and do not usually use social media.

The role of independent learning requires a big role from parents in guiding children to learn. From the data show that 35.6% of parents and teachers agree that parents are more important, even though parents cannot work alone, 63% agree that there needs collaboration between parents and teachers. Few say that the role of the teacher is bigger.

This is also in line with the research of SIGAP and the Disability Network in 2020, the pattern of independent learning with parents is mostly carried out in children with disabilities who live in rural areas (GTK DikmenDikus, 2020). Considering that access to communication in rural areas is not as easy as in urban areas, internet facilities and communication devices are also an obstacle. In addition, not all regions of Indonesia have special or inclusive schools in their regions.

As also stated that the constraints of curriculum services in schools and the unavailability of accompanying teachers for children with special need make parents who do not have this access to school let their children to learn independently at home. For parents who are accustomed to independently educating their children, they stated that in this pandemic situation the role of parents is very important in accompanying children, does not really have an impact furthermore, the parents responded positively to this situation. 55.2% of them stated that online activities at home meant that they had more time together with their children.

Parents' involvement is very much needed, because in this pandemic, when children have learning needs at home required the parents who play more of a role as teachers for children. According to Webster-Stratton &Bywater (2015), a supportive learning environment will contribute to school readiness and achievement at school, especially in language development. This also applies to children with special needs.

The Obstacles of Children with Special Need Service

The obstacles faced by parents and teachers in online learning are the network, the difficulty of teaching online that the parents do not understand how to help their children to learn, and the rest is because no one accompanies the children to study at home. Considering that children with special needs relatively need individual handling, the level of children's independence is the key to their success in completing the tasks given by the teacher.

Barriers to children's understanding of the subject of learning are 58.7% subject knowledge in the fields of mathematics and science, then Indonesian Language, and other subjects. There are some children have problems in all subjects. 40.4% of children have communication problems which become obstacles to the independent learning process so that children need assistance in class. Other problems are related to independence, social interactions, and difficulty showing expressions/emotions so that children easily behave destructively, such as cranky and bad mood when studying.

Figure 13 Obstacle of SBK Service

Problems related to children's learning barriers in communication aspects, are; children have difficulty understanding other people, do not focus on speaking, children's language is difficult to understand, and often repeat words. This has an impact on children's understanding barriers to understand of subjects at school, and children's ability to make friendships, such as children who are difficult to accept their playmates, difficulty sitting still, preferring to be alone, and disturbing other people.

This causes children need individual learning accompaniment, and in the midst of this pandemic situation, the role of parents is important considering that children with special needs required a great assistance from their surroundings, need assistance in doing academic activities/ school assignments. Meanwhile, for children with special needs who have carried out activities independently, parents help to monitor children and work with teachers to create activities that can optimize children's growth and development.

Collaboration between school and teachers is needed so that parents are willing to be involved in assisting children to study at home. According to Hallahan, Kauffman and Pullen (2014) actually with the involvement of parents in children's learning, this can strengthen the bond between parents and children with special needs. It's just that sometimes parents do not understand how to engage and support children. Therefore, efforts are needed to increase collaboration and understanding for parents and teachers.

Furthermore Hallahan, Kauffman and Pullen (2014) explain that teachers need to provide assignments that allow children to complete. Thus students do not refuse to do assignments. Assignments also need to be related to the learning that has been given in class (Hallahan, Kauffman and Pullen (2014). Coordination with other teachers who provide other tasks needs to be done so that the assignment is not overloaded. Parents need to be given explanation on how to assist their children while studying and doing their homework. It would be better if students are given homework that is functional. If a child face behavioral problems, it is very important for the school and parents to carry out a functional behavior analysis so that the cause of the behavior problem can be found. In addition, it is necessary to discuss interventions that can be carried out (Kumar Jaiswal 2017).

Teachers need to make various adaptations, especially with long distance learning during this pandemic. Kirk, Gallagher, Coleman and Anastasiow (2012) explain that adaptation in terms of the learning environment, curriculum adaptation, adaptation of teacher teaching strategies, and adaptation in terms of tools and the use of technology need to be done in the learning of children with special needs. Therefore, teachers need to make various adaptations for the success of children's learning.

Conclusion

During the pandemic, the challenges faced in education services for children with special needs stem from various obstacles because of the need for great assistance when children learn. Parents need to be willing to

spend time and have to understand how to assist children in learning. Teachers and parents need to work together and establish good communication, so that parental involvement can increase. Teachers need to adapt various things in learning, so that students can adapt learning to the needs and conditions of each student. Several things need to be done, including identifying the needs, uniqueness, and strengths of students in order to provide the right program. Good communication between the school and parents needs to be established so that parents understand how to assist children in learning at home. Training and mentoring for teachers to increase their knowledge and skills in modifying materials, teaching strategies, and evaluating learning outcomes need to be done. The use of technology aids and scheduling in the implementation of learning programs is one of the keys that encourages the successful learning of children with special needs.

Acknowledgements

The authors are very grateful to the KemenristekDikti, Faculty of Islamic Studies, University Of Muhammadiyah Jakarta, experts, LPPM University of Muhammadiyah Jakarta, teachers, and parents who have contributed to various components of this research.

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